

ANALYSIS OF NATAL HOROSCOPE OF PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Determining career in a horoscope is a challenging task nowadays. In ancient time or in the past, the job or professional areas were very little, but today it is as vast as the sea. If you take a job or a career, there are many categories. The government, the private sector, the IT sectors, In this article the researcher tried to high light the ways and means in the study of horoscope prediction – determination of teaching career in private organization.

Key Words: Teacher, Private School, Jupiter, Mercury, Sun Saturn, Mars, Kindergarten, Primary, High School

Introduction:

There is a saying that the profession itself is a God where we need to give reverence and respect to it. It refers to the value of a profession or career which we are carrying out. Mother, Father, Guru, God - Here the word Guru refers to the teacher. From this we can well understand the importance of the teacher. The teaching profession is a sacred profession. The teacher is responsible for being the best guide for the students in guiding them. A good teacher accepts the responsibility of guiding students on the right path. Becoming a good teacher by resolving students' doubts and correcting their mistakes is a very special career. A good teacher not only teaches students but also teaches them discipline and self-control.

Teacher:

Teaching is the noblest profession. Next to parents, teachers are also responsible in molding the characters and helping the children to have a bright future in their life. As the water in the well secretes, A teacher will increase his knowledge and energy by teaching their knowledge to others. Education is different. Teaching is different. A few will study very well. But they are not able to explain it to others. Others will excel in education as well. They also have the ability to teach it to others. There are subdivisions in the teaching profession as there are subdivisions in all other professions. There are primary education teacher, higher level teacher and Higher secondary level teacher. It can be divided into private school and public school teachers. There will also be sections depends upon the course they are teaching. A few will teach all the lessons. Some will teach only math. While some others may specialized in only one field, such as science, language, history, and geography, and work as a teacher in that field. Mercury and Jupiter must be strong in one's horoscope to be a good teacher. They must be in good condition to receive fame and name in the profession. Only if the sun is strong, then only they can get a job Government school.

Montessori School Teacher:

Montessori school teacher needs the creative skill to teach the students. The class rooms of the Montessori are beautifully crafted to create the atmosphere needed for the children's range. It needs many aids to meet the requirement of the children. They have to meet out the real interest with the available resources. It needs creative power of the teacher. They should be very cautious in terms of safety of the children. Awareness and alertness are needed. Mercury is responsible for the creative power and intellectuality here. They need motor skills and language skills.

Play School Teacher or Kindergarten Teacher:

Playschool teacher plays an important role in Child's life. Children are learning new stories, morals. They help the children to differentiate shapes, colors, identifying the objects, also helps the children to eat properly. Inculcate the habit of mingling with their peers. They are next to mother of that child. They need to undergo certain special training to become a play school teacher. They are nurturing the children in all ways. They need patience rather than anything. In a horoscope if strong mercury or Jupiter is posited in a favourable form for teaching profession and they are posited the star Kritika, we can say they can choose playschool teaching job. As Kritika is a star which represent the mother character who nurtured six children (Muruga). They need to express their love and affection towards children. For this Venus position will help us to decide.

Primary Teacher:

Primary Teachers are playing an important role in a child's life. The way of teaching, showing love and affection, taking care of the child's interest and encourage them to learn. By seeing the teacher's approach and his / her attitude, the child imitates. If the teacher is very soft and polite the child shows interest in going to

school, wants to learn new and good things and become a bright child. If the teacher is harsh and rude, the child is very much reluctant to go to school, resist to eat, sometimes in fear or in misbehavior.

Secondary School Teacher:

By the time, the child enters the secondary school, shows enthusiasm and follows the teacher. Sometimes Teacher becomes the student's role model if the teacher rude or tough with students or taunting the students, chances are there that the child becomes so arrogant, naughty mischievous etc., some may avoid to come to school. Some teachers are really interested in teaching. They are not merely teaching but also imparting the knowledge. During the explanation of the meaning of the poem, they will take us to those particular periods as if we are watching the live program. They make the student to love the subject and excel in the subject. Some teacher's partiality behavior makes the student to develop the hatred feeling towards the subject. But few teachers, with their talents in teaching, make the dull or below average students or disinterested in studies also, help the pupils to score good marks in the exams. The teachers from Primary, secondary, Higher secondary, various college teachers from arts, Science, Commerce, Engineering, Medical, Technical fields, Extracurricular activities are playing a very important role to make their students excel in their chosen field n help them to shine in their fields. They are the sole responsible with their dedicated service to create a future teacher, dancers, doctors, lawyers, Engineers, Architect, leaders, National leaders. Make them to feel really interested in the welfare of their subjects, Some teachers are highly knowledgeable and have done their Doctorate course. But due to their personality, dressing sense, not mingling with the present scenario unable to impress the students and are expelled from the teaching profession. Thus the teachers next to the parents are to be worshipped and to give due respect to the teachers and to salute such a noble profession.

The History of Jupiter:

According to Vedic Astrology, the planet Jupiter is considered as the God Guru. According to Mahabharata, Brihaspati is the son of Maharishi Angira. Jupiter also represents Brahma of mythological scriptures. Thursday is the day of the week dedicated to Guru. Therefore, the Guru is worshiped on this day. Jupiter's color is yellow. In the scriptures, the Guru is considered the embodiment of modesty and dharma. Thus, we can understand how extensive is the importance of Jupiter planet in astrology with astronomical and religious point of view. The other names of Jupiter are Guru, Bruhaspati. The planet is the ruler of the signs Sagittarius and Pisces. Jupiter represents knowledge, education, charity, virtue and religious work. Guru is the auspicious planet in the Navagrahas. His vision will take one to a higher place. If Guru yoga is there in one's horoscope, even the poor will be elevated to the level of rich and accumulating wealth for seven generations. If there is Guru yoga in one's horoscope, the person may get respect from others. Guru is the giver of Loyal relationships, goodwife, and children and close friends. If a person has Guru Yoga in the horoscope, that person will be looking for higher positions in politics. Strong Guru will make a person credited with learning the intricacies of the law and the subtle arts of performing puja according to the rules of the temple scriptures. Guru is the one who gives determination. The one who can give enough gold. Giver of the privilege of enjoying native possessions. The Guru is the giver of the blessings that awaits from the deeds done. Guru Bhagavan gives children and makes children excel and give benefit from them and gives them and a happy life without worries.

Significance of Jupiter:

Jupiter represents fortune, wealth, charity, fame, luck, devotion, children, faith, spirituality, teachers, morality, meditation, mantra, magistrates, ministers, lawyers and leaders in government and religion. Jupiter represents wisdom, sacred scripture, benevolence and philosophy. Jupiter's most favoured position is in the first. He does well both in the Kendra's and Angles, and the auspicious Trikonal Houses. His nature is watery. His gemstone is Yellow Sapphire or Yellow Topaz and his metal is Gold. Jupiter's direction is Northeast and his day is Thursday.

Career and Jupiter:

Jupiter is the largest planet in the Solar System. Guru (Jupiter) is considered the most auspicious planet among the nine planets of astrology. Guru is mainly the factor of developing spirituality. Jupiter is associated with places of pilgrimage and temples, holy rivers and religious activities. Jupiter is considered to be the factor of working in many types of fields like teachers, astrologers, philosophers, writers. Jupiter has been said to be more effective for studies and teaching. Apart from this, Moon, Mercury also attract people in this area in the form of helpful planets. If seen on the basis of zodiac, if there are signs of Jupiter or Mercury in the Ascendant, second, sixth, tenth house in the birth chart, then due to their influence the person becomes more interested in teaching. Whenever he gets the opportunity, he also starts working as a teacher.

Significance of Mercury:

The planet Mercury plays a very important role in astrology and controls very special components of our life. The color of Mercury is green, Varna is Vaishya, Mercury is the lord of Gemini and Virgo, Virgo is also the exalted sign of Mercury and in Pisces, Mercury is debilitated, i.e. weakest, Saturn, Venus and Rahu are friends of Mercury. Mercury is the planet of your tongue, behavior, your mind and your beauty. The position of Mercury in the horoscope decides how you speak, how you behave, your personality and intelligence. In astrology, Mercury is considered to be intellect, reasoning, decision ability, memory, ability to think, speech,

speaking ability, pronunciation, tact, information, communication, transport, business, commerce, calculative subject, writing, skin, beauty and Fragrance is considered to be a factor of communication and in-depth study.

The history of Sun:

In Hindu mythological texts, the Sun is considered a deity, according to which, the Sun is the soul form of all living beings. Through this a person gets life, energy and strength. According to popular belief, Surya is the son of Maharishi Kashyap. Due to the mother's name being Aditi, one of the names of Surya is Aditya. In astrology, the planet Sun is said to be the factor of the soul. Among nine planets sun is considered as the king planet. In any kind of profession sun represents the status of that person in the profession. It represents the administrative power, leadership quality, courage, bold behaviour etc., which are required to shine in one's profession. In the person's livelihood, the Sun represents government office. Makes the person a principled person, in addition to this, Sun makes a strict discipline officer in the field, a high position officer, administrator, progress with time, creator, supervisor of works. In astrology, the title of king has been given to the Sun, according to astrology, the Sun represents the soul and the father. All the planets receive light from the Sun. Surya is the form of the direct deity who runs the universe. Sun is also considered representative of ancestors in the horoscope. If one or more malefic planets influence the Sun in any horoscope, Pitru Dosh is created in that horoscope. If sun is malefic in particular person's horoscope or in debilitation position or posited in 6th 8th 12th place is the reason for not getting the government job.

Saturn:

According to astronomy, Saturn is a planet that has rings around it. It is the sixth largest planet from the Sun and the second largest in the Solar System after Jupiter. This yellow planet. Saturn's atmosphere consists of about 96 percent hydrogen and 3 percent helium gas. According to astronomy, there are hundreds of natural satellites located on the rings of Saturn. Although officially it has 53 satellites. In Hinduism, the planet Shani is worshiped as Shani Dev. In mythological scriptures, Shani is considered the son of Sun God. There is such a description in the scriptures that Surya had refused to accept Shani as his son because of the dark complexion. Since then, Shani keeps the house of enemy from the Sun. Elephant, horse, peacock, deer, donkey, dog, buffalo, vulture and crow are the rides of Shani. Shani maintains harmony in this earth and punishes the person who does bad deeds. In Hindu religion, on Saturday, people observe a fast in the worship of Shani Dev and offer mustard oil to him.

Significance of Saturn:

Saturn signifies longevity, obstruction, delay, servants, death, travels in forests, destruction, iron, oil, representation of low caste people, failures learning a language other than his mother tongue untruthful, pleadings, angry, mental worry, cruel, bad friends, defective organ, windy diseases, paralysis, Dental diseases Elephantiasis, and lean constitution, slow, adoption. horses, elephants, skins, troubles, indigestion, debts, punishments, fines, imprisonment, travelling in foreign countries, disappointments, loss of money, bad habits, smallpox, Kingdom, mean work agriculture profession, etc.

Planetary Combination in a Horoscope of a Private Teacher:

- Jupiter and mercury is quite strong or aspect each other in the horoscope
- Conjunction of 5th and 10th lord in the 6th house.
- Mercury conjunction with 5th or 10th house lord
- If Mercury placed in 2nd house with 5th, 6th or 10th lord.
- The planet of Knowledge and wisdom Jupiter placed, aspect or any connection with 2nd 6th and 10th house then the person will do the teaching profession.
- Jupiter placed in the 5th house or as 5th lord placed in 10th house
- If Jupiter in 5th or 7th house and aspect to 10th lord from anywhere by both Lagna.
- 5th lord and 6th lord in 2nd house and Jupiter aspect to 10th lord or placed in 10th house.
- The conjunction of 2nd, 5th 6th and 10th lord and Jupiter aspect on that conjunction then the person will be a good teacher.
- 10th lord and 9th lord aspect each other or conjunction give teaching job.

Horoscope:

Name: Kanaka Lakshmi.G.

Gender: Female

Date of Birth: 07.05.1971

Time of Birth: 1.30 A.M.

Place of Birth: Kalapakkam, Thiruvannamalai

Ve	Me Su	Sa	
As	Rasi D1		Ke
Ma Ra			
	Ju		Mo

Ma	Me Mo		
Ke	Navamsa D9		
Ve Sa			Ra
	As	Su Ju	

As	Me	Ra	Ve
	Dasamsa D10		
Sa			Mo
	Su Ma Ke	Ju	

Rasi Chart Analysis:

Ascendant falls in Aquarius. The Second Lord is Jupiter and is posited in 10th house. Venus the fourth Lord posited in second house in Mercury's Star Revathi and aspects the sixth Lord moon posited in 8th house. It receives Jupiter's fifth aspect. Karmakarak Saturn, the Lagna Lord is posited in 4th house. The Fifth house Lord Mercury is posited in 3rd house along with sun the 7th lord. The 6th Lord is Moon and is posited in 8th house. From there, it aspects the second house. Ketu is posited in 6th house and receives Jupiter's 9th aspect. Jupiter is posited in 10th house and aspects the Lagna lord Saturn through its 7th aspect. Mercury is in same sign in Navamsa chart as in Rasi chart which is in vargothama.

Interpretation:

As the 4th house makes a relation with 2nd and 11th house, it made the native to had a prosperous career as a teacher. Earns income from more than one sources. Also, she can gain unexpected income through her teaching profession. Though the native can earn good income, she may face some hurdles at the work place. She may not get the co-operation of the colleagues. She feels as she may be isolated at works place.

Dasamsa Chart Analysis:

Dasamsa Ascendant as well as 10th Lord is Jupiter and is posited in 8th house. Mercury is in Aries as in Rasi chakra and Navamsa. Moon is posited in 6th house.

Interpretation:

Native may earn from more than one source. She may get unexpected income through teaching profession. Moon indicates mother and mother tongue. Hence the native chooses the profession as Language teacher.

Rules Applicable:

4th lord connection with 2nd house and 11th house makes the native to have a teaching profession. The Jupiter's aspect falls on the second house is the reason for the native to earn through the teaching profession. The Jupiter's aspect falls on the sixth house is the reason for the native to get a job in teaching profession.

Name: Madhan Raj.D

Gender: Male

Date of Birth: 25.07.1984

Time of Birth: 9.30 A.M.

Place of Birth: Vanuar, Villupuram

Ve	Me Su	Sa	
As	Rasi D1		Ke
Ma Ra			
	Ju		Mo

Ma	Me Mo		
Ke	Navamsa D9		
Ve Sa			Ra
	As	Su Ju	

As	Me	Ra	Ve
	Dasamsa D10		
Sa			Mo
	Su Ma Ke	Ju	

Rasi Chart Analysis:

Ascendant falls in Leo. The Second house Lord Mercury is in Leo sign i.e., posited in Ascendant and it receives the 9th aspect of Jupiter. Here budha gets Dig bal too. 4th Lord is posited in Jupiter's star Vishakha. Fifth house Lord Jupiter is strongly posited in its own house and aspects Ascendant through its 9th aspect. It receives Saturn's 3rd aspect. 10th Lord Venus is posited in Mercury's Star Ashlesha and posited in 12th house along with Sun.

Interpretation:

As the fourth Lord is Mars which is in Jupiter star made the native as a sports and physical teacher. The native has the best quality of a teacher. The native may get name and fame in his profession because the Jupiter is in fifth house. Sun which is 12th place made the native to work in a private firm and has no chance to get the government job. He may acquaintance wealth through his own earnings from teaching profession.

Dasamsa Chart Analysis:

Ascendant Lord Venus is posited in 5th house. Mercury is in second house and the 10th Lord Saturn is posited in 11th house along with Jupiter. Mercury and Venus are favourable sign in Dasamsa. And both aspects each other.

Interpretation:

It indicates income through teaching profession. Sun is posited in Ascendant. The native will become the head of the department or office or organization. 10th Lord in 11th house indicates the gain through profession. Being a sports coach the native can have contact with all the students. It indicates the huge network. The native can have a large social circle in the organization. The native will get name and fame from his profession.

Conclusion:

Scholar discusses about the facts and Astro planetary connectivity involve in ascertaining the prediction of private school teacher with the support of the framed rules. The proven rules and usage of Dasamsa will be helpful in future for the astrologers to predict about career as a teacher in private schools.

References:

1. JatagaAlankara – Keeranur Natarajan
2. BrugathParasra Hora Sastra- Sagar publications
3. Manthiresvarar – Phaladeepika
4. Saravali
5. JathagaChandriga